
MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM AS ADJUVANT IN THE TREATMENT OF SLEEP BRUXISM – PROTOCOL PRESENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Bruxism was defined in 2014 through the International Classification of Sleep Disorders, as a repetitive jaw muscle activity that is characterized by clenching or grinding of teeth. Bruxism has two different circadian manifestations, which can occur during wakefulness (awake bruxism) or during sleep, called Sleep Bruxism (SB). Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is an integrative technique that is based on the dissociation of charges in the body, usually caused by a thermal variation in two specific points. The charges that are vibrationally and energetically related are induced and depolarized through the use of magnets that emit static magnetic fields of medium intensity, correct or prevent the pH distortion of organs or tissues in the living organisms. As a result, the neutralization of pathogenic bioelectrical distortions promotes health.

Objective and Method: The objective of this work is to present the MB therapeutic technique through the Sleep Bruxism treatment protocol, which can be used by health professionals or Biomagnetism therapists as a complementary practice in the management of SB and its causes. The methodology used to compose this protocol was descriptive bibliographical research of an exploratory nature in books and articles. **Conclusion:** As a result, the Sleep Bruxism Protocol (SBP) was presented, allowing to treat and attend to the organic and emotional imbalances that trigger SB.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Static Magnetic Fields; Magnets; Integrative and Complementary Practices; Sleep Bruxism; Biomagnetism Protocol.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Brazil, 29 Complementary Integrative Health Practices (*PICS – Práticas Integrativas Complementares à Saúde*) were regulated by the Unified Health System (*Sistema Unico de Saúde – SUS*) (BRASIL, 2018). The emergence of a more holistic medicine that meets the needs of the integral health state of the human being can be observed all over the world (MENDES, *et al.*, 2019; LUZ, 2019).

Integrative medicine gains strength as a new model in health and is defined as the combination of conventional and non-conventional medicine. This gives the patient the chance to choose the most appropriate form of treatment. Currently, therapeutic techniques offer an integrative treatment that considers the human being as a whole composed of body, mind and spirit (OTANI *et al.*, 2011).

MB fits into this context, as a complementary health technique based on bioelectric, biomagnetic and bioenergetic principles (GOIZ DURÁN, 2005; BRASIL, 2006; DAVIS, 1974).

The MB is a technique that uses magnets that generate magnetism, influencing the body's electricity (bioelectricity), and this, in turn, influences the body's Biochemistry (pH), in order to reach homeostasis. According to Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán (2008), the imbalance in organic homeostasis and, in consequence, the pathological and pathogenic manifestations, are created from two poles, a South

pole that attracts the positive charges of biochemical elements, such as H⁺, and a North pole which attracts negative charges, such as OH⁻. A biochemical structure in which its elements remain in magnetic resonance, is called a Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

The BMP is formed when charges that are in resonance with each other exceed the limits of organic entropy, an essential condition for homeostasis and health. The MB is based on the distortion of two specific points for each pathogenic microorganism or tissue dysfunction, which are out of physiological balance tending towards an excess of alkalinity or acidity, out of the limit of relative neutrality, where nature conditions organic homeostasis and health (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008) .

The treatment with MB is carried out through Static Magnetic Fields (SMFs) generated by magnets. The south pole (positive as per MB convention) of the magnet repels the positive charges of the biochemical elements and the north pole (negative as per MB convention), repels the negative charges. To understand this concept, it is essential to understand a fundamental principle of electricity and magnetism: The Universal Law of Charges (FRANCISCO *et al.*, 2007; GOIZ DURÁN, 2003). With impaction, which is the application of magnets on the imbalanced charges, a chemical reaction will occur and the charges will be neutralized (LEHNINGER *et al.*, 2005). As a result, water is formed (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

Thus, organic entropy can be recovered and health can be achieved, as long as the organ or tissue has not reached an irreversible limit of the degenerative process (GOIZ DURÁN, 2003; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; GOIZ DURÁN, 2014).

The SMFs generated by neodymium magnets used in MB are of moderate intensity, ranging from 1,000 to 7,500 G (Gauss) or 0.1 to 0.75 T (Tesla). This margin is considered to be safe according to the National Center for Complementary and Alternative Medicine (NCCAM), which supports the scientific community to use them in daily practice (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; MARYCZ *et al.*, 2018; ZHANG *et al.*, 2017).

The beneficial clinical effect of low, moderate and high intensity SMFs has been demonstrated in research (PHILPOTT *et al.*, 2015; MARYCZ *et al.*, 2018). The lack of natural and weak SMF causes symptoms of insomnia, asthenia, depression and increases the risk of osteoporosis in humans. SMF can stimulate the movement of cellular ions and increase the use of oxygen by cells by activating integrins (proteins found in the cell membrane, responsible for mediating interactions between the extracellular and intracellular membranes). It can also modulate the cell cycle and metabolism with beneficial effects on pain control, nerve regeneration, inflammation, cutaneous microcirculation and blood flow (DE LA CAL, 2004; MARYCZ *et al.*, 2018).

In 1988, Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán, developer of the MB technique, participated in a course on the Energy Therapy system where Dr. Richard Broeringmeyer, US Space Agency physician described that SMFs can detect and correct pH distortions in a living organism and combining it with kinesiology to perform a scanning, he reported that the application of a SMF of 0.1 Tesla (T) or 1,000 Gauss was used to correct the shortening of the right leg of the first astronauts after returning to Earth (BROERINGMEYER 1991; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

Faced with these discoveries and studies, associated with other knowledge such as acupuncture and reflexology, Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán understood organic pathologies from a bioenergetic point of view, as well as their clinical correlation with the treatment of diseases through magnetic fields. Thus, the MB technique was developed considering that the neutralization of pathogenic bioenergetic distortions promotes health. The MB can be considered a disease prevention process when the pH distortion of the organs or tissues of the human body is corrected or avoided (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

In the field of dentistry and stomatology, other authors have already tested non-conventional techniques, including MB, to assess the change in salivary pH with the treatment of BMPs (ZAFERSON *et al.*, 2019).

Bruxism was defined in 2014 through the International Classification of Sleep Disorders (ICSD), as a repetitive activity of the jaw muscles that is characterized

by clenching or grinding of teeth (AMERICAN ACADEMY OF SLEEP MEDICINE, 2014).

The Sleep Bruxism (SB) has already been considered one of the most devastating para functions of the oral cavity, since it is constant, unconscious and generates excessive loads for the dental and periodontal tissues (sustaining periodontium), which can bring severe damage to the Stomatognathic System (SS) as a whole (HANSON *et al.*, 1995). Currently, the construction of the bruxism concept seems to change from a parafunction to a possible physiological or protective motor activity. According to these recent studies, the SB comes to be considered in some cases, a protective and physiological muscular activity and not a parafunction. This reflects the current SB paradigm shift in some cases from pathology to behavior, *i.e.* muscle activity (MANFREDINI *et al.*, 2021).

Large-scale epidemiological studies have been conducted internationally to assess the prevalence of SB in the population as a whole; these show that the number of SB cases in the population ranges from 4.4 to 31.4%. Other studies, which evaluate SB in more specific populations, show a higher prevalence, even reaching 50.2%, as in the case in which military personnel were studied. The results of these studies, however, cannot be used as an estimate for the entire population (PONTES, 2019).

The SB is a multifactorial disorder whose cause is still not fully understood. The possible causal factors can be divided into: peripheral (morphological) and central (pathogenic and psychological). We can point out the following as causal factors of SB: genetics; emotional stress; use of stimulating substances such as caffeine, alcohol, cocaine, tobacco; specific medications and some neurological pathologies, such as Parkinson's disease (PONTES, 2019).

Although SB is not a life-threatening disease, it can influence the quality of human life, especially through dental problems. The most obvious symptoms are: abnormal tooth wear, masseter hypertrophy, pain and injuries in the temporomandibular joints (TMJ), sensitivity and/or pain in the dental elements, dental discomfort and tiredness in the facial muscles when waking up, tension

headache, popping noises, crepitation and locks in the Temporomandibular Joints (TMJs), pain in the ears, tinnitus and changes in sleep stages where it may be involved in normal awakening events (MALULY, 2012; SOARES *et al.*, 2021).

There is no single specific treatment or cure for SB, as there is a lack of randomized clinical studies with longer follow-up time to verify the safety of treatments. Currently, behavioral, dental, pharmacological, physiotherapy treatments and their combinations are used, according to the case of the patient with SB, to relieve symptoms (BADER, 2000; SERAIDARIAN *et al.*, 2001).

There are many protocols used by Biomagnetism practitioners today. Most were created from the clinical practice of MB, observing the BMPs that were most repeated during the complete scanning protocol of different individuals and that were found during the treatment of specific pathologies (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; 2019).

This is a pioneering and innovative study since the synergy of conventional dental treatments of SB and MB has not yet been used. The objective of this study is to present the therapeutic technique of MB through the protocol for the treatment of SB to serve as an alternative and/or non-invasive complement that is comfortable, painless, low-cost and that can be integrated with other treatments.

2. METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive bibliographical research of an exploratory nature, based on a literary review, with the aim of proposing a protocol treatment for SB using the MB technique. A bibliographic survey was carried out and the concepts and ideas of the authors were analyzed, confronting the study objectives, building an analysis of the object to justify the use of the MB technique in the treatment of SB. A description of the physiology, pathophysiology of SB and the MB technique was presented, as well as the steps for creating the protocol and the line of thought to reach conclusions about the BMPs chosen to compose the Protocol for Bruxism (GIL, 1991).

Publications available in the bibliographic databases of PubMed and Google Scholar, covering the period from 2005 to 2021, were considered. The descriptors used were Medicinal Biomagnetism; Static Magnetic Fields; Integrative and Complementary Practices; Sleep Bruxism; Biomagnetism protocols.

The inclusion criteria used for the selection of articles was that they were contemplated in at least one of the stipulated descriptors and that they were not from the period prior to 2005, available online, in Portuguese, Spanish and English.

Exclusion criteria are related to articles that do not meet the study theme, and do not answer its guiding question, as well as articles not available in full.

Based on the bibliographic survey, we were able to gather 466 BMPs described in the literature that were studied in detail, taking into account the therapeutic effect resulting from their depolarization, through the application of SMFs. Thus, we chose and gathered, in the form of a treatment protocol, the BMPs most commonly related to SB, their causes and repercussions.

This survey aimed to provide the necessary literary basis for the development of a protocol with BMPs suitable for the SB condition. After the exploratory study of the selected materials cited at the end of this article, the Sleep Bruxism Protocol (SBP) was created.

Due to the scarcity of publications of MB, SMF, Biomagnetic Pair and *PICS* (Complementary Integrative Health Practices – *Práticas Integrativas Complementares à Saúde*), books from local libraries, theses and handouts from courses were included and there was no restriction on the period of publication. Duplicate works and works that did not cover the theme were excluded.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study resulted in a literary review of 3,003 articles selected from PubMed and Google Scholar databases. After applying the exclusion criteria, 28 articles remained, as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Articles considered for the study

Caption: *PICS* (Complementary Integrative Practices in Health / *Práticas Integrativas Complementares à Saúde*); MB: Medicinal Biomagnetism; BP: Biomagnetism Protocol; SB: Sleep Bruxism; SMF: Static Magnetic Field.

After defining the 28 articles in the literary bases, books, theses and course handouts were selected and 185 works were found. 3 references from government websites with content related to the theme, 1 reference from a website of an American professional society, 1 website and 2 handouts from the Par Magnético Institute (IPM) as well as 22 books were included. After applying the exclusion criteria, 57 works referenced in this study remained.

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TABLE 2: Sleep Bruxism Protocol (SBP)

BMP	North Impact Point (-)	South Impact Point (+)	Specification	Symptomatology / Semiology of BMPs	Result / Discussion
BMP1	R Ear	L Ear	Special Pair	Trigeminal neuralgia, bruxism, tension headache, nervous tics, facial paralysis, strabismus, CNS sequelae, traumatic brain injuries, dental pain. It improves the function of the 12 pairs of cranial nerves and the basal ganglia. Helps in the treatment of poisoning.	According to Dr. Goiz Durán (2008), this BMP is indicated for the treatment of the symptoms of bruxism, including neuralgia of the trigeminal nerve (GOIZ DURAN, 2008). The motor innervation of the masticatory muscles originates in the trigeminal motor nucleus. Although the cortex plays a prominent role in oral motor activity, the brainstem is responsible for balancing homeostasis and controlling the body's unconscious functions (MALULY, 2012). SB is described as an involuntary trigeminal motor activity, linked to microarousals, with specific jaw movements during sleep, whose modulation is still unknown (AZEVEDO, 2018).
BMP2	Superior cerebellum	Inferior cerebellum	Special Pair	Bruxism, Parkinson's. This pair can relieve seizures.	SB has been observed together with neurological or psychiatric diseases, such as Parkinson's disease, depression or schizophrenia and when it occurs in the presence of pathologies of this nature, it is considered to be secondary.(LAVIGNE <i>et al.</i> , 2003).

BMP3	R Armpit	L Armpit	Regular Pair (Rabies Virus)	Laryngitis, otitis, chronic sinusitis, bronchitis, asthma, neurological problems, personality changes, irritability, muscle twitches, macular edema, photophobia, blindness, retinal degeneration, allergies, uveitis, parathyroid dysfunction, parotid dysfunction, false Alzheimer's.	In the researched bibliography it was observed a correlation between muscle twitches or contractions caused by rabies virus and SB symptoms. According to official document signed by the head of state in Brazil that can be found under "Portaria SDA/MAPA 168/2005", animals infected with the Rabies virus may present, among other symptoms, muscle tremors, teeth grinding, and involuntary muscle contractions (MACIEL, 2005).
BMP4	R Kidney / L Kidney	L Kidney / R Kidney	Reciprocal Pair (<i>Clostridium tetani</i>)	Muscle spasms, trismus, tetany, opisthotonos, sudden muscle contractures.	The bacterium <i>Clostridium tetani</i> is responsible for releasing the toxins tetanolysin, tetanospasmin and the non-spasmogenic toxin, causing the pathology of tetanus. It was observed by Mozelli Filho (2019), that an animal with clinical signs of tetanus, presented tetany, bruxism, among other symptoms.
BMP5	R Mandible Angle	L Mandible Angle	Regular Pair (<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>)	Oral diseases, gingival diseases, acne, canker (mouth ulcer), carious lesions, TMJ stiffness, periodontitis, laryngitis, rhinitis, pharyngitis, otitis, nosebleeds.	A cross-sectional study carried out at the Department of Dentistry, Sri Manakula Vinayagar, Medical College & Hospital, India, demonstrated that the risk of carious lesions related to bruxism in children aged 4 to 7 years is high. This study thus relates the presence of oral bacteria with bruxism (PRIYA, 2019).
BMP6	R Superior Preauricular	L Inferior Preauricular	Special Pair	Ear disorders, ear pain from water or pressure difference, bruxism, maxillomandibular disorders, TMJ stiffness.	Anatomical region of the TMJ in which several facial muscles are inserted. These muscles and the TMJ itself can suffer inflammation and dysfunction as a result of SB (PEIXOTO, 2021).

BMP7	Pineal	spinal bulb	Regular Pair (Multiple viruses)	Guillain Barré Syndrome, false Alzheimer's, polyradiculoneuropathy (acute with prolonged evolution, dependent on the Immune System's integrity), demyelination of spinal nerve roots and peripheral nerves (after an infectious condition), muscle weakness (of rapid progression), paralysis of limbs and respiratory muscles, fatigue, dizziness, sleep apnea, heavy legs, dandruff, asthenia, drowsiness, insomnia, irritability, nausea, headache, malaise (jet leg effect).	There seems to be a paradigm shift from parafunction SB pathology to physiological and protective muscle reflex behavior against sleep apnea (MANFREDINI <i>et al.</i> , 2021). There may be a significant association between SB and insomnia. Studies show that among individuals diagnosed with insomnia, 16.5% had SB, while, among those who were not diagnosed with insomnia, only 8.0% had SB (MALULY, 2012).
BMP8	R Superior jaw	L Superior jaw	Regular Pair (<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>)	Trigeminal neuralgia, eye problems, migraines, deafness, mastitis, phlebitis.	One of the characteristics of SB is the excessive stimulation of the muscles of mastication, through their motor innervation (mandibular nerve V3), originating from stimuli from the central nervous system (PINHEIRO, 2020).
BMP9	Liver	Heart	Psychoemotional Pair	Wrath	The SB is commonly attributed to factors of psychological origin. The patient suffering from SB may be expressing anger or tension and developing the unconscious nervous habit in response to unresolved personal problems or the impossibility of expressing feelings of anger and aggressiveness (HANSON <i>et al.</i> , 1995). These emotions can release chemicals in response to a stimulus. When a chemical substance binds to a cell through a specific receptor for it, a given organ may have more receptors for that molecule and less for another type of molecule. In the emotions of BMPs 9, 10, 11 and 12, the receptors begin to create resistance as a result, more receptors are produced to try to recapture the molecule that is there in abundance. In this way, the
BMP10	Cerebral Amygdala	thymus	Psychoemotional Pair	Hate	
BMP11	R Temporal	R Temporal	Psychoemotional Pair	aggressiveness	
BMP12	R Lung	L Lung	Psychoemotional Pair	Guilty	

					affected tissue or organ can become overloaded and become unbalanced (PALMA-GUDIEL, 2015; COOPER <i>et al.</i> , 2005; MARSHALL <i>et al.</i> , 2016).
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Caption: BMP = Biomagnetic Pair; R = right; L = left; CL= contralateral, IPS= ipsilateral. **Source:** The authors, based on Bossa (2023), Goiz Durán (2003, 2008 and 2014) and Goiz Martínez (2017 and 2018).

For a better visualization of the SBP being impacted by the MB magnets,an illustrative image presented in Figure 1 was created.

FIGURE 1 – Anatomic representation of the SBP hologram:

Caption: The figure shows the BMPs of the Sleep Bruxism Protocol (SBP). The figure is a representation of a photograph of BMPs impacted with MB magnets on the body. The red color indicates that the north pole, the black face of the magnet, is in contact with the skin. Likewise, the black color indicates that the south pole, the red face of the magnet, is in contact with the skin. **Source:** The authors and Bossa (2023).

In order to systematize the application of the Sleep Bruxism Protocol (SBP), it is recommended to carry out 2 Complete Scanning (CSs) of MB (Bossa 2023) before its application, with an interval of 8 days between them. The CS aims to ensure that the individual needs are met. All BMPs in the SBP must be impacted, in no defined order, for 50 minutes, at least 3 times, with an interval of 5 days between each protocol application. After this period of treatment, it is necessary to reassess the patient's signs and symptoms, and the CS is repeated (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018). SBP can be reapplied as many times as the Biomagnetism therapist believes to be necessary. As shown in Figure 2.

After the first CS, some important general recommendations should be considered such as having the patient change the toothbrush, pillowcase and bed linen (as well as everything that is in contact with the patient's saliva). According to Dr. Goiz, these procedures must be adopted to avoid possible cross-contamination, as well as to rule out the hypothesis that the treated BMPs are related to viruses housed in saliva. It is recommended that the pillars of health be strengthened (healthy eating, regular physical exercise and stress control). Finally, the Biomagnetism therapist must assess the patient's reactions and improvements to the treatment (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2017).

The SBP should not be applied without evaluation by the Biomagnetism therapist in individuals with bioelectric devices such as pacemakers, cochlear implants and others, as well as in pregnant patients, especially in the first trimester of pregnancy, and also in patients who have already undergone radiotherapy and chemotherapy treatments. It should never be applied to hemodynamically unstable patients. (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; BOSSA, 2021a).

Even though the MB is such a broad technique, it is still not included in the list of *PICS* offered in the *SUS* (Brazilian National Health System) allowed by the Health Regulatory Agency in Brazil, but it is offered by Biomagnetism therapists serving voluntarily or informally in hospitals and various City halls' social projects. This fact did not prevent the practice of this complementary technique from enduring for the last 30 years, in private practices and solidarity actions. Some protocols were studied, improved and created for the treatment of various

dysfunctions in organ systems, such as immunological, endocrinological, lymphatic, vascular protocols, among others (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2019; BOSSA, 2021b; BOSSA, 2023).

Doctor Isaac Goiz Durán developed a unique protocol known as Complete Scanning (CS) of MB. The BMPs that constitute the CS have been published in several books, according to the chronology of their discovery, other BMPs have been cited in courses. In order to group all BMPs into a single material, the Postgraduate program at Par Magnético Institute (IPM) edited a compilation of all the BMPs researched by Dr. Goiz, identified as the Medicinal Biomagnetism Scanning Protocol (BOSSA, 2023).

The identification and systematization of the BMPs that are related to bruxism presented in Table 2 were selected among them.

The MB protocols, in general, are presented as quick reference guides, to scan with the magnet the most important points to provide care for an specific symptom and/or to prophylactically impact different organic systems as well as BMPs by diseases, if necessary (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2017).

Geomagnetic interference phenomena are characterized by considerably affecting the depolarization length of time of the BMPs to the users of this technique. The further away a user is from the equator, at both geographic poles of the planet, the longer the depolarization duration will be. In the equatorial zone, the depolarization time of BMPs ranges from 3 to 5 minutes, while in countries close to the geographic poles, it can last from 45 to 50 minutes (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018). To ensure the scope of the SBP application within these limits, the maximum time was established, which is 50 minutes, which may, according to the Biomagnetism therapist's knowledge, be adjusted according to the patient's needs.

FIGURE 2 – Simplified scheme for using SBP

Caption: min.= minutes. **Source:** The authors. The recommended therapeutic break between the 2 CSs is 8 days, according to the recommendation by Goiz Martínez (2018). According to this author and Goiz Durán (2008), the application of CS can trigger a biological process of greater entropy, due to the biochemical and immunological reactions that occur as a result of the depolarization of charges in the body. After this organic stabilization, the pause between the application of SBP can be reduced, as it will not trigger the same entropic effect observed previously, since the organism already has a more organized bioelectricity (GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

Alternatively, to reduce the application time of the magnets, both in the CS and in the SBP, it is possible to follow Dr. Asunción Zeferino Martinez Elena (2022), physicist at ESFM University, IPN, Mexico. He advises that the time of depolarization of the BMPs when the body of the patient has the head facing the Magnetic North of planet Earth, is reduced of 10 minutes, no matter the latitude in which he is found. In this case, 2 compasses and a ruler must be used on the stretcher to position the user in the recommended way, as shown in Figure 3 (ELENA; MARTÍNEZ, 2022).

FIGURE 3 – Use of compasses and ruler to determine the direction of the Earth's North Pole.

Source: (ELENA; MARTÍNEZ, 2022)

It is important to mention that studies have shown the existence of interference between the various Magnetic Fields (MFs) generated by living beings, in addition to the possibility of the action of MFs applied to organisms. The ability of magnetoreception by living cells was identified. The study by Eder and his collaborators (2012), demonstrated the capabilities of candidate cells to be magnetoreceptors for MFs. It was highlighted that cells from the sensory epithelial tissue of trout are capable of perceiving MFs. This perception may be associated with magnetoreception in other living organisms and animals (EDER, *et al.*, 2012).

Furthermore, researchers at the University of Tokyo, using a custom-built microscope, demonstrated that flavin-based autofluorescence in untreated native HeLa cells are sensitive to MF. (IKEYA and WOODWARD, 2021). Another study by the same author provides a direct link between the effects of the magnetic field on chemical reactions measured in solution and the chemical reactions that occur in living cells (IKEYA and WOODWARD, 2021). In another research, the concentration and region distribution of brain magnetite was examined by magnetic remanence measurements of fresh/frozen tissue samples, Alzheimer's disease as well as in normal brains from the Manchester Brain Bank (MBB), UK. (HAMMOND *et al.*, 2021).

These studies may be associated with the need for a pause between MB applications and also with the magnetoresistance identified in some BMPs and specific microorganisms. Even so, the practice of MB, in terms of the treatment of BMPs, with therapeutic and specific magnets for the technique, is considered safe when the application criteria are respected and the general recommendations are followed. The application of MB magnets is similar to magnetotherapy. In the MB, magnets are applied in pairs on the BMPs, with opposite poles between them and systemic action (bipolar use – with North and South Pole of the magnet being used). In Magnetotherapy, one pole is applied (monopolar use), where the magnetic pole applied to the body depends on the therapeutic objective and its action is local (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

The Magnetotherapy with low-frequency MFs has been officially approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for use in orthopedic injuries, in cases of pain and edema in superficial soft tissues (MARKOV, 2007). Currently, medium- and high-intensity SMFs generated by magnets are used in medicine for both diagnosis and treatment, as is the case with Magnetic Resonance Imaging that uses 1T to 3T MF (10,000 G to 30,000 G) and Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) where the MF intensities can be regulated by the operator depending on the type of pathology treated and brain region (MARKOV, 2017).

Exposure to mild to moderate intensity SMF has been shown to improve cartilage and bone regeneration (JABERI et al., 2011), reduce inflammation and degenerative changes in cases of articular osteoarthritis in humans, reduce pain and improve clinical status of patients with arthritis and rheumatoid arthritis, accelerate new bone formation (MENG et al., 2013), prevent the decrease in bone mineral density, as well as induce cartilage metabolic activity (SAYFZADEH et al., 2007), improve circulation (XU et al., 2007) in addition to promote edema reduction and having an antiinflammatory effect (MORRIS et al., 2008).

Studies suggest that magnetotherapy through Pulsed Magnetic Fields has applicability in diseases such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's (MARKOV, 2007).

The magnets mentioned in this MB study emit medium intensity SMFs (from 0.1 to 0.75 T). These have been identified as an important therapeutic tool in human and animal regenerative medicine. The potential biomedical application of SMF has been studied in relation to its beneficial effects on health (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; PHILPOTT et al., 2015; ZHANG et al., 2017; GOIZ MARTÍNEZ, 2018; MARYCZ et al., 2018), since it does not produce physical damage, has few and not long lasting side effects when used with magnitudes considered safe (BECK et al., 2011).

Evidence of the effectiveness of MB has already been demonstrated against infectious diseases (GOIZ DURÁN, 2005). It was observed that some BMPs are related to the presence of microorganisms such as viruses and bacteria, including *Salmonella typhi*, whose infection was described by Frank (2017), which instigates further investigation into the involvement of microorganisms in the pathogenesis of SB. In this study, an evaluation of patients' response to treatment exclusively with MB for *Salmonella typhi* infections (typhoid fever) was performed. Most participants retested as negative and all patients reported clinical and symptomatic improvement (FRANK, 2017). For MB, these conditions may be related to the existence of BMPs such as BMPs 4, 5 and 8 of SBP, which affect the normal function of cells, tissues and organs and may also maintain antigens such as endotoxins or microorganisms (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

According to the literature review, it was identified that BMPs 9, 10, 11 and 12 of SBP seem to recover the balance of tissues or organs affected by negative emotional states and emotional stress, a major trigger of SB (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

Therefore, the BMPs indicated in the SBP composition are related to signs and symptoms of the pathology. The identification of the BMPs involved in each particular case will be found in the CS, which contains 466 BMPs, and the treatment will be reinforced with the application of SBP aiming at improving the individual's quality of life with the total or partial recovery of the SB.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Considering the Sleep Bruxism (SB) an illness that affects many people, lacking of new therapies to be integrated into the list of treatment possibilities, in a complementary and alternative way, and MB being a safe, non-invasive and easy-to-apply practice, the Sleep Bruxism Protocol (SBP) can be a beneficial, low-cost, minimal-risk strategy that seems to contribute satisfactorily to the control of SB and its causes.

This unprecedented study represents the first that points to the use of a MB protocol to aid in the treatment of SB and may stimulate further studies in this field that are likely to produce important discoveries.

It is expected that this protocol will be integrated into the therapeutic approach to be used in individuals with SB and will be the first step towards new discussions about alternative and complementary measures adopted for the prevention and treatment of this disease.

Thus, the present study considers the applicability of the practice of the SBP of the MB as a future perspective, in the format of clinical trials, so that evidence can be presented.

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